

HOW TO IMPROVE PRONUNCIATION THROUGH USING MIRROR IN THE LEARNING PROCESS, ITS BENEFITS AND USING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, it is becoming more and more popular for people to have a lot of challenges with speaking while they learn a new language. Especially, the most problematic areas they experience is actually connected with pronunciation, they cannot produce some sounds correctly and struggle with having the right approaches to work on them. On this case, the best way to improve for my mind would be using mirrors in the right way. This article aims to show its benefits and analyze the right ways in using mirrors.

Key words: mirror, reflection, confidence, speaking skills, presentation, pronunciation features, daily objects;

INTRODUCTION

Most people suffer with improving their speaking because of their pronunciation difficulties. In order to improve not only speaking, but also pronunciation, there are hundreds of techniques given by a number of researchers. But today, by writing this article, I want to show a weird but effective way of improving pronunciation. From history, we actually know that people used a lot of tools to Improve their overall speaking skills. However, I think that mirror thing can also help to improve pronunciation. Because while practicing in front of mirror, one thinks and controls his/her own actions. That practicing person becomes aware of his mistakes and watches how his/her teeth, lips, tongue movements and has the chance to analyze and reflect. Also, this way is really fast way of improving. "Mirrors help you overcome that "pickle-faced" look that so many of us carry around with us in business. Indeed, when I left the practice of law and got into the training business, I spent a great deal of time in front of the mirror, working on smiling and just getting more animated." (Joey Asher, 2019);

I can actually say that mirror is the reflection of us, in which one can individually and truly can see himself/herself as he/she is and start improving as a result of working on faulty areas.

MAIN PART

To start, a considerable number of people believe that mirror is just a tool to see our outlook, to comb hair and such stuff. But it can also be of great value in language learning. Mirrors are typical household furnishings for many people. However, did you realize that they can also be utilized to prepare for the OET Speaking sub-test? It can not only help you gain confidence for presentations and speaking, but it can also assist you with visualizing pronunciation.

“Mirroring entails careful study of a video of an original “model” speaker of L2, including both verbal and non-verbal behavior, followed by a video recording of the L2 learner performing the same monologue or dialogue as the original speaker. Mirroring has been studied in a multiphase “Mirroring Project,” conducted at the International Teaching Assistant (ITA) Program at the University of Minnesota, in which graduate students build awareness of L2 identity. One of the most important parts of this project is that each student chooses his or her “model” speaker to mirror.” (Colleen Meyers, 2018);

Let’s look at them in details. Firstly, practicing over and over, one will develop a look of himself in front of mirror and gets used to it, which will later helps learners to feel ok, even if they go to the stage in front of thousands of people due to their confidence levels.

Also, it is worth to mention that our body organs get into shape when they feel under observation and this observation comes with looking at the mirror. For example, the tongue can easily change its movement while pronouncing words. For this, just a learner needs to practice this for several times so that one can really improve over a period of time with less effort and productivity.

Having said these things above, one more key advantage of using mirrors being independent and rarely relying on another person to get help or to Coach. To illustrate this, people say that they really need someone by their sides to control and analyze their actions, but by using mirror both coach and learner is the same person and can do pronunciation exercises in any time possible in everywhere without relying on another person or waiting others. Additionally, there are more benefits that comes with this process itself. Being able to practice on own and becoming happy of having the ability to do it independently, this gives a muscle of confidence to a learner.

As well, there is one more thing called mirror affect, which can have both positive and negative outcome for each other. Mirror effect is something in which people see themselves and make up their mind about their looks. While this happens, some people find themselves really attractive and will develop narcissistic personality, and some start hating themselves as well they will get into complaining about their outlooks especially, in our topic, individuals may

complain about their tongue movements, eye contact and facial expressions they make. In this case, they may change to positive side. Because they start working on themselves and alternate their movements into more beautiful socially accepted styles, in which comes good changes in one's pronunciation. As you can see, a lot of benefits are possible because of using mirrors in the learning process.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there are a lot of different opinions about improving pronunciation in the learning process. However, I think that some weird called and less used modern techniques can actually work a lot. The use of mirror is also a great way to develop and enhance pronunciation. This paper work intends to see and discuss the benefits of this technique.

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